

EFFECT OF LAGOS STATE COVID-19 ACTION RECOVERY ECONOMIC STIMULUS ON WELFARE OF ARABLE CROP FARMERS IN IKORODU, LAGOS STATE

PAUL TEMEGBE OWOMBO

*Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension,
Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa
Ondo State, Nigeria*

Email: owombopaul@gmail.com, +2348032207213

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effect of the Lagos State COVID-19 Action Recovery and Economic Stimulus (CARES) program on the welfare of arable crop farmers in Ikorodu Local Government Area (LGA) of Lagos State. Data were collected from 120 randomly selected arable crop farmers who were beneficiaries of the program in the study area. Descriptive research design approach was employed to obtain quantitative data, using self-designed structured questionnaires through interview schedule from the respondents. The results indicate that majority (65%) of the respondents were male and the mean age of the respondents was 46 ± 11.25 . The mean farming experience was 8 ± 4 years while the mean farm size was 1.63 ± 0.90 ha. Regression analysis results revealed that Lagos State CARES program's financial support ($p \leq 0.01$) and infrastructural development ($p \leq 0.01$) had positive and significant effect on welfare of arable crop farmers in the area through improved income generation. The training and capacity building also -had positive but non-significant relationship with the welfare of arable crop farmers in the study area. The study concludes that Lagos State CARES program improved welfare of arable crop farmers in the study area. The study recommends that government and her agencies should make provisions for intervention programs for the purpose of enhancing farmers' welfare, especially during disaster period.

Keywords: COVID-19 pandemic, Lagos CARES program, arable crops, welfare.

JEL Codes: I38

1. INTRODUCTION

Farming is an important occupation in Nigeria, providing livelihood for many households. The known challenges facing farming in Nigeria include pests and diseases, increasing climate variability, poor holdings among smallholder crop farmers and extremes weather, which negatively impacts food systems and rural livelihoods (Arua *et al.*, 2025). In 2020, these challenges became aggravated following the difficulty created by the Covid-19 pandemic that shut down every sector of the economy, including agriculture. The world, Nigeria, inclusive, faced unprecedented challenges as a result of Covid-19 pandemic with significant negative effects on the society as a whole (Hammanjoda, 2020; Ado and Yaro, 2023)). The COVID-19 pandemic severely impacted public health and disrupted economic and social structures of Nigeria and the world at large (Ajibo *et al.* 2020; Okhankhuele, 2020, Sopko *et al.*, 2020). Arable crop farmers were particularly affected due to supply chain disruptions, limited market access, and financial struggles compounded by pre-existing challenges like resource scarcity, climate change, pest and diseases and inadequate infrastructure (Obisesan and Adeboye, 2021). To address these issues, the Nigeria COVID-19 Action Recovery and Economic Stimulus (NG-CARES) program was launched, with its implementation in Lagos State known as Lagos CARES.

NG-CARES, a two-year emergency response initiative by the Federal Government of Nigeria in collaboration with the World Bank, aimed to mitigate job losses, support micro and small enterprises (MSEs), and sustain basic services (World Bank, 2022). It aligned with the

government's broader goal of lifting 100 million Nigerians out of poverty within a decade. In Lagos, a group of beneficiaries of the program were arable crop farmers in Ikorodu, with the primary aim of addressing poverty and enhancing welfare among them.

Lagos CARES employed a multifaceted strategy, providing financial relief, enhancing productivity, improving market access, and offering skills development. Recognized in a World Bank report on COVID-19 recovery in developing countries, the program serves as a model for global post-pandemic recovery efforts (World Bank, 2022). Additionally, it aligned with Nigeria's Economic Sustainability Plan (ESP), which allocated NGN 2.3 trillion (US\$6 billion) to prevent business collapse, create jobs, invest in infrastructure, boost local production, and protect vulnerable populations (Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, 2020).

The program operates through three key result areas: increasing cash transfers and livelihood support for poor households, enhancing food security and supply chains, and supporting household and micro-enterprise recovery, which are enhancement tools for people's welfare. Therefore, the study was conducted to examine the effect of Lagos CARES on arable crop farmers' in Ikorodu LGA of Lagos State.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Literature

Covid-19 is an acronym that stands for Corona Virus Disease 2019 as named by the World Health Organization (WHO) and named after the year of discovery. The disease is an infectious disease caused by the discovered coronavirus, and it was first discovered in the December of 2019 in China. COVID-19 was considered to be very contagious and that led to its quick spread through human-to-human transmission to many countries around the world (Harapan *et al.*, 2020; Ado and Yaro, 2023). On 30th January 2020, WHO officially declared the COVID-19 an epidemic as a public health emergency of international concern, and later on 11th of March 2020, COVID-19 was transformed to a pandemic. COVID-19 was a deadly virus that attacked not only the health of individuals but also that of the entire world economy (Ado and Yaro, 2023). In addressing the economic problem created by the disease, national and international organisations made interventions to reducing the effects on populations. In Nigeria, government and its agencies introduce intervention programs to addressing the social, economic, and other challenges caused on the population, particularly, vulnerable groups by the COVID-19 pandemic (Okhankhuele, 2020).

The Lagos CARES Program emerged as a strategic response to the economic disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Launched as a multi-sectoral initiative, it aimed to mitigate the socio-economic challenges faced by vulnerable populations, with a particular focus on revitalizing the agricultural sector. This section provides a detailed examination of the Lagos CARES Program, encompassing its objectives, components, and the anticipated effect on the welfare of arable crop farmers in Ikorodu, Lagos State.

Components of the Lagos CARES Program

- i. **Financial Support for Farmers:** One of the key components of the Lagos CARES Program is the provision of financial support to farmers. This assistance takes various forms, including direct cash transfers, grants, and subsidized credit facilities. By injecting capital into the agricultural sector, the program aims to address immediate financial constraints faced by farmers and stimulate increased productivity (Lagos State Government, 2023).
- ii. **Capacity Building and Training:** The Lagos CARES Program incorporates a robust capacity-building component. This involves training sessions, workshops, and extension services aimed at equipping arable crop farmers in Ikorodu with

- the necessary tools to enhance their agricultural practices, adopt modern technologies, and improve overall productivity (Lagos State Government, 2023).
- iii. Infrastructure Development: The program allocates resources to infrastructural development. This includes the improvement of irrigation systems, storage facilities, and transportation networks. By enhancing infrastructure, the program seeks to reduce post-harvest losses, improve market access, and create an enabling environment for sustained agricultural activities (Lagos State Government, 2023).

2.2 Empirical review

COVID-19 Action Recovery and Economic Stimulus Program Project for Nigeria aimed to expand access to livelihood support and food security services, and grants for poor and vulnerable households and firms (World Bank Group, 2020). This program was domesticated in the states in Nigeria, including Lagos State. Lagos CARES program provided financial, infrastructure and capacity building initiatives to the beneficiaries. Awotide & Agboola (2020) posited that the injected capital into the sector addresses critical needs of the farmers such as purchasing inputs, maintaining equipment, and investing in sustainable farming practices, which ultimately leads to improved livelihoods. They added that the financial support provided through the Program alleviates the immediate economic burden on arable crop farmers in Ikorodu local government area of Lagos State. Nwaobiala *et al.* (2024) reported that COVID-19 adaptation strategies had positive impact on arable crop farmers' output in the Umuahia agricultural zone of Abia State.

Awotide & Agboola (2020) reported that a combination of financial support and capacity building initiatives is expected to translate into increased productivity among arable crop farmers. They added that with access to modern techniques and technologies, farmers can optimize their farming processes, leading to higher yields and improved overall efficiency. Awotide & Agboola (2020) also reported that the Lagos CARES Program involves a multifaceted approach, including infrastructure development which addresses inadequate storage facilities and unreliable transportation that minimize post-harvest losses and improve the overall resilience of the agricultural value chain.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

This study considers and adopt human capital theory for the study

Human Capital Theory (Gary Becker in 1964)

Human capital theory was developed by Gary Becker in 1964. The theory viewed education, training, health, and experience as investments that increase a person's productivity and earning potential. The theory according to Becker, frames individuals as having human capital that can be accumulated, similar to physical capital that can be invested. Becker, added that there is a difference between general training and firm specific training, which is only valuable to the employer who provided it.

Human capital theory (HCT) is concerned with knowledge and experiences of small-scale business owners. HCT assumes that the human capital of the founder improves small firms' chances of survival and performance (Bruederl *et al.* 1992). The theory assumes that human capital which comes in terms of experience and knowledge acts as a resource that can translate to firms' productivity. It is noteworthy that human capital factors, such as length of managerial

or industry experiences or education, are not strong predictors of success, but usually, they are significant predictors (Bruederl *et al.* 1992, Rauch and Frese 2000).

The adoption of this theory for the study is premised on the fact that the Lagos CARES Program incorporates a robust capacity-building component, which involves training sessions, workshops, and extension services aimed at equipping arable crop farmers in Ikorodu with the necessary tools to enhance their agricultural practices, adopt modern technologies, and improve overall productivity. The HCT emphasized specific education, training and knowledge/skills as important tools for firms' survival or performance. The adoption of this theory implies that arable crop farmers who are trained or educated on specific improved farm production practices would translate same to improved productivity and hence, better welfare. Lagos CARES has incorporated capacity building programmes that has the potentials of enhancing farmers' productivity (Lagos State Government, 2023).

3. METHODOLOGY

Study area

The study was conducted in Ikorodu Local Government Area (LGA) of Lagos State. Ikorodu LGA was selected for the study because of the prominence of agricultural activities in the LGA and the LGA was a beneficiary of the Lagos CARES program. It is located along the Lagos Lagoon. The LGA shares boundary with Ogun State. It has Latitude 6^o 35^l 59.99^{ll} and Longitude 3^o 29^l 59.99^{ll}. The arable crops mainly grown in the area are maize, cassava, yam, cocoyam, vegetables, okra, etc.

Sampling procedure and Data

A simple random sampling technique was used to select 120 beneficiaries of the CARES program in the study area. The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane formula (Yamane, 1967), considering a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

n=required sample size

N= population size

e = margin of error

The data on the beneficiaries of the Lagos CARES program are presented in the table below as collected from the Lagos CARES Program: Impact Assessment Report (2023).

Table 1: Lagos CARES Program beneficiaries in Ikorodu

S/N	Local Government	Crop Type	Number of Farmers Benefitted
1	Ikorodu	Cassava	46
2	Ikorodu	Maize	35
3	Ikorodu	Vegetables	29
4	Ikorodu	Cocoa	19
5	Ikorodu	Plantain	42
	TOTAL		171

Source: Lagos State Government. (2023). Lagos CARES Program: Impact Assessment Report (Unpublished).

Yamane formula as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

n = required sample size

N = population size (171 arable crop farmers in Ikorodu)

e = margin of error (5% or 0.05)

Plug in the values:

$$n = \frac{171}{1 + (171 * 0.05^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{171}{1 + (171 * 0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{171}{1 + 0.4275}$$

$$n = \frac{171}{4275}$$

$$n = 119.78$$

The calculated sample size, *n* is approximately 120. Therefore, the required sample size for the study, using the Taro Yamane formula, is approximately 120 respondents.

Method of data analysis

The data for the study were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive analysis such as frequency count, simple percentages and mean scores were used. The inferential statistics used for the study was Multiple Linear Regression Model (MLRM).

Model specification

The Multiple Linear regression model

The structure of the model is specified as

$$Y = f(X_i) + \varepsilon_i$$

Y = dependent variable

X_i = independent variables

ε_i = error term

Empirically, the regression model is specified as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + \beta_6X_6 + \beta_7X_7 + \varepsilon_i$$

Y = Dependent variable (welfare of arable crop farmer measured by income)

X_1 = Age of respondents

X_2 = education of respondents

X_3 = Household size

X_4 = Membership of cooperative society

X_5 = Financial support score

X_6 = Training and capacity building score

X_7 = Infrastructural development score

$\beta_1 - \beta_2$ = represents the coefficient of independent variables

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Socio-economic characteristics of respondents

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents based on their socioeconomic characteristics. The results presented in the table revealed that the mean age of the respondents was 46 ± 11.25 years. This showed that the respondents were in their active ages. The mean household size was 5 ± 2.3 , which implied that family labour can be used as a means to reducing cost of production. The mean farming experience among the respondents was 19 ± 7.9 years, which implied that the respondents were well experienced. The mean farm size cultivated by the respondents was 1.63 ± 0.9 hectares. This implied that the farmers were operating at a very small scale. The mean of respondents' access to credit was 0.69 ± 0.62 . This implied that just 69 percent of the respondents had access to credit in the study area. The high percentage of respondents who had access to credit was traced to the Lagos CARES financial support. The mean of access to extension was 0.98 ± 0.81 . This implied that 98 percent of the respondents had access to extension in the production year. This high proportion was traced to the capacity building intervention of the Lagos CARES program.

Table 1: socioeconomic characteristics of Arable crop Farmers

Socio-economic characteristics	Mean	Standard deviation
Age (years)	46	11.25
Household size	5	2.27
Farming experience (years)	19	7.9
Farm size (ha)	1.625	0.90
Access to formal credit (dummy: 1 = yes, No = 0)	0.69	0.62
Extension contact (dummy: 1 = yes, No = 0)	0.98	0.81

Source: Field survey, 2024

Regression analysis results of the effect of CARES on farmers' welfare

Table 2 reveals the regression analysis result of the effect of CARES program on the welfare, measured by the income of the respondents. The regression results revealed that the R-square value of the model was 0.59, which implied that 59 percent of the variations in the dependent variables is being explained by the specified independent variables. The results also showed that education (≤ 0.01) of the respondents significantly influenced the welfare of the respondents. This implied that respondents who are educated would be capable of apply improved farming technologies that are capable of enhancing their incomes. The results further shoed that CARES intervention variables had positive and significant effects on the welfare of the respondents. The financial support score (≤ 0.01) had positive and significant effect on the income of the respondents. The finding revealed that an increase in the financial support score by a unit would raise respondents' income by 17.6 percent. This implied that an increase in financial support would raise their purchasing capacity to buy inputs that would in turn raise their output and by implication their incomes. This is in agreement with Nwaobiala *et al* (2024) that post Covid-19 intervention supports impact agricultural livelihood. The results also showed that infrastructural development score ($p \leq 0.01$) had positive and significant effect on the incomes of the farmers. The findings showed that an increase in the infrastructural development scores by a unit would raise respondents' income by 1 percent. The finding implied that when infrastructure like good road network is in place, market would be accessed, hence, produce can command good prices and by implication better incomes. This indicates that the CARES program had significant effect on the respondents' welfare. This is in

agreement with World Bank. (2022) that Covid-19 recovery intervention has positive impact on welfare of the beneficiaries.

Table 2: Regression analysis results of the effect of CARES on farmers’ welfare

Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	t-value	Sig.
Constant	2.336	2.350	0.994	0.320
Socioeconomic variables				
Age	-0.050	0.035	1.428	0.151
Education	0.091***	0.022	4.136	0.000
Household size	0.266	0.244	1.090	0.275
Membership of cooperative society	0.021	0.010	2.100	0.023
CARES intervention				
Financial support score	0.176***	0.052	3.384	0.000
Training and capacity building score	0.044	0.061	0.721	0.562
Infrastructural development score	0.005***	0.001	5.000	0.000
R-square	0.59			

Source: Field survey, 2024

*Significant at 1% level

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The study revealed that beneficiaries of the program were in their active ages and had high household size. The beneficiaries were experienced arable crop farmers and operated at a very small scale. The Lagos CARES program’s financial support and infrastructural development had improved the welfare of arable crops farmers in the study area. Therefore, the study recommends an introduction and implementation of intervention programs that would provide financial support, infrastructural development and capacity building among arable crops farmers as a means of alleviating poverty in farming communities.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author is grateful to Ololade Shakira Ladoja who assisted in collecting data for the study. The author is also grateful to the Ikorodu Local Government Area of Office of Lagos State Covid-19 Action Recovery Economic Stimulus for providing the enabling environment and needed information that supported the research.

REFERENCES

- Adewumi, M. O. and Oguntade, O. M. (2017). Traditional and Modern Farming Practices in Ikorodu: A Comparative Study. *Journal of Sustainable Agriculture* 15(2), 78-92.
- Ado, B. and Yaro, I. (2023). COVID – 19 and Stock Market Volatility in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 8(1), 349–360.
- Ajibo, H. T., Peace, N., and Onuoha, E. C. (2020). Assessment of the impact of covid-19 pandemic in rivers state, Nigeria and government palliative measures. *Journal of economics and allied research*, 5(1), 147–156.
- Arua, R. N., Muomaife, R. C. and Ibe, J. C. (2025). Food Security Status of the Farming Households in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research* 10(2), 208-219.
- Awotide, B. A. and Agboola, J. (2020). Building Resilience in Agricultural Value Chains: The Role of Infrastructure Development. *Journal of Sustainable Agriculture* 17(3), 112-128.

- Dreze, J., & Sen, A. (2013). *An Uncertain Glory: India and its Contradictions*. Princeton University Press.
- Becker, G.S. (1964). *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- Bruederl J, Preisendoerfer P. and Ziegler R (1992). Survival chances of newly founded business organizations. *American Sociological Review* 57: 227–42.
- Hammanjoda, K. (2020). The Wave of Covid-19 Pandemic and Nigeria's Overdependence on Oil: The Challenges and Possible Solution. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research* 5(1): 139-146.
- Harapan, H., Wagner, A., Yufica, A., Winardi, W. Anwar, S. and Gen, A. K. (2020). Acceptance of a Covid-19 Vaccine in Southeast Asia: A Cross Sectional Study in Indonesia. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.00381>
- Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. (2002). National Programme for Food Security (NPFS): Policy Document. Abuja: FMARD.
- Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. (2020). Nigeria COVID-19 Action Recovery and Economic Stimulus (NG-CARES) Program.
- FMARD. (2011). Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA): Progress Report. Abuja: Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. FMARD. (2012). Growth Enhancement Support Scheme (GESS): Impact Assessment Report. Abuja: Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development.
- Frese, M. and Rauch, A. (2001). Entrepreneurship, Psychology of, Editor(s): Neil J. Smelser, Paul B. Baltes, *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, Pergamon, 4552-4556.
- Lagos State Government. (2023). Lagos CARES Program: Impact Assessment Report. Unpublished.
- Nwaobiala, C. U., Ahamefule, B. A. and Muojekwu, M. K. (2024). Effect of COVID-19 adaptation strategies on arable crop farmers' output in the Umuahia agricultural zone of Abia State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Sustainable Agricultural Research, Conscientia Beam* 11(2): 41-49.
- Obisesan, A. and Adeboye, M. A. (2021). Impact of COVID-19 on Arable Crop Farmers: A Case Study of Ikorodu, Lagos State, Nigeria.
- Ogunlade, I., Adeyemo, R. and Arokoyo, T. (2020). Climate Change and Food Security: Evidence from Arable Crop Farmers in Southwest Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 266, 110577.
- Okhankhuele, O. T. (2020a). Root Tubers Expansion Programme (Rtep) and Quality of Products of Micro-Scale Cassava Processors in Oyo State Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research* 4(4): 80-97.
- Okhankhuele, O. T. (2020b). Covid-19 Lockdown and Price, Availability, Accessibility and Affordability of Rice in Akure Metropolis, Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research* 5(1): 73-90.
- Rauch, A. and Frese, M. (2000). Psychological approaches to entrepreneurial success: A general model and an overview of findings. In: Cooper C L, Robertson I T (eds.) *International Review of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*. Wiley, Chichester, UK, pp. 101–41.
- Sopko, J. T., Ijirshar, V. U. and Asom, S. T. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on social security in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 4(4), 144-160.
- World Bank (2015). Commercial Agriculture Development Project (CADP): Lessons Learned

and Best Practices. Washington, DC: World Bank.

World Bank. (2019). Lagos Agro-Processing, Productivity Enhancement, and Livelihood Improvement Support (APPEALS) Project: Implementation Completion and Results Report.

Washington, DC: World Bank.

World Bank Group (2020). Nigeria - COVID-19 Action Recovery and Economic Stimulus Program Project (English). Washington, D.C.: World Bank

Group. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/142411608260520935>. Accessed 8th November, 2025.

World Bank. (2022). COVID-19 Recovery Efforts in Developing Countries: Case Study of Lagos, CARES Program.

Yamane, T. (1967). *Statistics: An Introductory Analysis* (2nd ed.). New York: Harper and Row.

Yeap. (2013). Youth Empowerment in Agriculture Program: Evaluation Report. Abuja: YEAP.